

A New Spectrophotometric Determination of Adrenaline

Y. K. KOTHARI and K. SRINIVASULU*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain-456 010

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Adrenaline is estimated by a new and direct spectrophotometric method after developing a colour with ammonium molybdate, sodium nitrite in presence of diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA) in aqueous medium. The system absorbs maximum at λ 465 nm at room temperature. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range 0.8×10^{-5} – 1.2×10^{-4} M adrenaline. The Sandell's sensitivity of the estimation (for $A=0.001$) is 3.76×10^{-7} M adrenaline.

A number of methods are reported for the determination of adrenaline (catecholamine). Loew¹, Gaddum and Schild² observed that alkaline oxidation of adrenaline yielded a yellow-green fluorescent compound³ 1-methyl-3,5,6-trihydroxyindole (THI, also called adrenolutine). A semi-automated THI technique was first described using an autoanalyser system⁴. Notelson⁵ examined the reaction between adrenaline, ammonia and a number of organic primary amines and described an assay for adrenaline using ethylenediamine. Bronu⁶ carried out a specific colour reaction of adrenaline in presence of sodium nitrite or potassium nitrite. Bloor and Bullen⁷ evaluated a number of colorimetric assays and attempted to estimate human venous plasma adrenaline concentration. Adrenaline has also been determined by gas liquid chromatography⁸ and high performance liquid chromatography⁹ methods.

In the present paper, the spectral behaviour of adrenaline with ammonium molybdate, sodium nitrite and DTPA in aqueous medium is presented.

Experimental

A Beckman 26 spectrophotometer was used for the spectral studies.

Adrenaline (Sigma) solution was prepared in concentrated H_2SO_4 (B.D.H.) (0.5 ml). The ammonium molybdate and sodium nitrite (S. Merck) and DTPA (Koch-light) solutions were prepared in distilled water. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Effect of pH: Preliminary investigations were carried out to find the optimum pH range for the estimation. It was observed that the absorption maximum at λ 465 nm (Fig. 1) persists (when using a mixture of 6.0×10^{-5} M adrenaline with 8.0×10^{-5} M ammonium molybdate, 4.0×10^{-5} M sodium nitrite and 4.0×10^{-5} M DTPA) over a pH range 4.2–5.4 and the absorbance value remained the same in the pH range 4.5–5.2. Hence pH 5.0 ± 0.1 was chosen for studies.

Fig. 1. Spectrum of adrenaline, ammonium molybdate system in presence of sodium nitrite and DTPA; adrenaline = 6.0×10^{-5} M, ammonium molybdate = 8.0×10^{-5} M, sodium nitrite = 4.0×10^{-5} M, DTPA = 4.0×10^{-5} M, pH = 5.0 ± 0.1 .

Effect of ammonium molybdate concentration: Adrenaline (6.0×10^{-5} M), sodium nitrite (4.0×10^{-5} M), DTPA (4.0×10^{-5} M) and varying concentration (0.2×10^{-5} – 2.0×10^{-5} M) of ammonium molybdate were mixed at pH 5.0 ± 0.1 and the absorbance was measured at 465 nm. The colour saturation for this system was found to be in the concentration range 1.2×10^{-5} – 2.0×10^{-5} M ammonium molybdate. Hence the concentration 1.6×10^{-5} M of ammonium molybdate was selected for further studies.

Effect of sodium nitrite concentration: Adrenaline (6.0×10^{-5} M), ammonium molybdate (1.6×10^{-5} M), DTPA (4.0×10^{-5} M) and varying concentration (8.0×10^{-6} – 6.0×10^{-5} M) of sodium nitrite were mixed at pH 5.0 ± 0.1 and the absorbance was measured at 465 nm. It was found that the colour saturation was obtained in the concentration range 4.0×10^{-5} – 6.0×10^{-5} M sodium nitrite. Hence the concentration of 4.8×10^{-5} M of this reactant was chosen for further studies.

Effect of diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA) concentration: For the above system adrenaline ($6.0 \times 10^{-5} M$), ammonium molybdate ($1.6 \times 10^{-5} M$), sodium nitrite ($4.8 \times 10^{-5} M$) and varying concentration ($0.2 \times 10^{-5} - 1.2 \times 10^{-5} M$) of DTPA were mixed at pH 5.0 ± 0.1 and the absorbance was measured at 465 nm. The data indicate the colour saturation for the system to be in the range $0.4 \times 10^{-5} - 1.2 \times 10^{-5} M$ DTPA. Hence the concentration $0.6 \times 10^{-5} M$ of DTPA was selected for further studies.

Time effect: The absorbance value of the mixture containing adrenaline ($6.0 \times 10^{-5} M$), ammonium molybdate ($1.6 \times 10^{-5} M$), sodium nitrite ($4.8 \times 10^{-5} M$) and DTPA ($0.6 \times 10^{-5} M$) was measured at different time intervals at pH 5.0 ± 0.1 and the absorbance value was measured at 465 nm. The data indicate that the colour saturation for the system was obtained 45 min after mixing the solution but attains stability after 45 min and remains constant upto 90 min. Hence the experiment was carried out after 45 min and before 90 min of preparation of the solutions.

Effect of adrenaline concentration: The optimum concentration range for the estimation of adrenaline was found to be $0.8 \times 10^{-5} - 1.2 \times 10^{-4} M$ and confirms Beer's law. Beyond the $1.2 \times 10^{-4} M$, Beer's law is not obeyed under the conditions of study. Sandell's sensitivity¹⁰ (for $A=0.001$ and 1 cm path length) is $3.76 \times 10^{-7} M$ of adrenaline, and the molar extinction coefficient 3250. The relative standard deviation (r.s.d.) for six samples at $6.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ level is 0.64% and confidence limit¹¹ at 99% C.L. is $6.0 \times 10^{-5} \pm 0.106 M$.

Procedure: In aqueous medium, ammonium molybdate ($1.6 \times 10^{-5} M$), sodium nitrite ($4.8 \times 10^{-5} M$), DTPA ($0.6 \times 10^{-5} M$) and varying concentration ($8.0 \times 10^{-6} - 1.2 \times 10^{-4} M$) of adrenaline were mixed and pH was adjusted to 5.0 ± 0.1 . The absorbance was measured at 465 nm against reagent blank after 45 min and before 90 min of mixing the solutions.

Effect of foreign ions: The following ions $\times 10^{-5} M$, in parenthesis were tested for their interference in the determination of adrenaline by the procedure, which did not contribute any significant error in the estimation of $4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ of adrenaline: Li^I (9.27), Na^I (24), K^I (18.4), NH_4^+ (13.5), Ag^I (0.14), Hg^{II} (0.044), Mn^{II} (7.07), Cu^{II} (5.01), Ni^{II} (5.44), Co^{II} (5.02), Ba^{II} (3.18), Sr^{II} (2.24), Ca^{II} (6.8), Fe^{III} (1.52), chloride (9.65) bromide (4.03), iodide (0.7), acetate (4.4), sulphate (0.24) and tartrate (2.13).

Results and Discussion

Adrenaline in presence of ammonium molybdate gives an intense yellow colour with λ_{max} 338 nm. However, in the system in presence of DTPA the colour intensity decreases. Adrenaline in presence of sodium nitrite gives a light pink colour with an absorption in the range 460–500 nm, but the colour fades with time. If the sodium nitrite and DTPA are present together in the system of adrenaline and ammonium molybdate, the orange colour intensifies and shows an absorbance maximum in the range 465–480 nm. The colour intensity of the solution remains stable in this case. To confirm that this colour was obtained only with this combination of reactants, various alternative combination of mixtures, like ammonium molybdate + sodium nitrite; ammonium molybdate + DTPA; sodium nitrite + DTPA; ammonium molybdate + sodium nitrite + DTPA; adrenaline + DTPA (all these colourless); adrenaline + ammonium molybdate (light yellow colour, λ 338 nm); adrenaline + sodium nitrite (light pink colour, 460–500 nm); adrenaline + ammonium molybdate + DTPA (light yellow colour, 330 nm); adrenaline + sodium nitrite + DTPA (light pink colour, 460–500 nm); adrenaline + ammonium molybdate + sodium nitrite (orange unstable colour, 465–485 nm) were prepared at the same pH and scanned, their absorption bands being given in parenthesis. This confirms that the combination of adrenaline, ammonium molybdate, sodium nitrite and DTPA, gives a orange-red colour with λ_{max} 465 nm. The absorbance value remain same after 45 min of preparation of the solution and upto 90 min.

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